

MAKING YOUR ORGANISATION'S INFORMATION ACCESSIBLE FOR ALL

IMPLEMENTING THE GUIDELINES FOR ACCESSIBLE INFORMATION

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European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education, 2015

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The ICT for Information Accessibility in Learning project is a multi-disciplinary network of the following European and international partners, representing learning and ICT communities:

DAISY Consortium

European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education

European Schoolnet

Global Initiative for Inclusive ICTs

International Association of Universities

United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization

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ABSTRACT

This guide has been produced for organisations that wish to provide accessible information both in the education sector and more widely.

It should be used in conjunction with the Guidelines for Accessible Information (the Guidelines) and is one of the outcomes of the ICT for Information Accessibility in Learning (ICT4IAL) project [<http://ict4ial.eu/>]. This and other useful materials on the website are open educational resources and can be freely distributed.

Accessible information is understood as information provided in formats that allow every user and learner to access content 'on an equal basis with others' (Article 9, United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities – UNCRPD). The recommendations and implementation models in this guide are based on the experiences recorded in evaluation reports by three organisations involved in the project:

- the International Association of Universities
- European Schoolnet
- the European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education.

They trialled the draft Guidelines that had been previously developed by the project. This pilot activity resulted in revisions to the Guidelines and their practical experiences are at the core of this guide. In addition, the recommendations developed by the predecessor project, Accessible Information Provision for Lifelong Learning (i-access) [<http://www.european-agency.org/agency-projects/i-access>], and expert advice on this topic have also informed the content.

In implementing accessible information, based on the Guidelines, in your organisation we recommend the following:

- 1) Include an accessibility statement in the organisation's long-term strategy.
- 2) Develop a strategy or plan for implementing accessible information.
- 3) Make someone responsible for implementing the information accessibility plan and provide them with the required resources.
- 4) Plan an incremental implementation – be ambitious and modest at the same time.
- 5) Embed accessibility into your information production and dissemination processes.
- 6) Provide information, education and training on accessibility for all staff.
- 7) When outsourcing information production, make sure accessibility requirements are addressed and undergo a quality check.

This document contains details of each recommendation, along with a model of how your organisation could implement the Guidelines.

Two appendices are also provided. The first, Appendix A – Guidelines for Accessible Information Audit Tool, is a useful template your organisation could use when auditing content. The second, Appendix B – Implementation Reports Template, is the template used by the organisations involved in the trial implementation of the Guidelines to provide feedback.

We hope that you will find the guide useful, and we welcome feedback. In addition, we invite you to share with us your experiences of implementing information accessibility for learning. Details of how you can do so appear in the Conclusion section of this guide and on the ICT4IAL project website.

INTRODUCTION

This publication is intended to be used with the Guidelines for Accessible Information [<http://ict4ial.eu/guidelines-accessible-information>] (the Guidelines), which were developed by the ICT4IAL project [<http://ict4ial.eu/project-aims>]. The implementation recommendations that follow are the result of pilot implementations of the draft Guidelines. The pilots also resulted in revisions that led to the final version of the Guidelines.

The ICT4IAL project was a multi-disciplinary network of European and international partners, representing both learning and ICT communities, that ran between 2013 and 2015. It built on the results of the Accessible Information Provision for Lifelong Learning project [<http://www.european-agency.org/agency-projects/i-access>] to foster information accessibility in learning. The European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education (the Agency) acted as project co-ordinator. The Agency, together with European Schoolnet (EUN), the International Association of Universities (IAU), the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), the DAISY Consortium and the Global Initiative for Inclusive ICTs (G3ict) aimed to:

- raise awareness and increase the visibility of the issue of accessible information provision and its relevance for equitable lifelong learning opportunities;
- support accessible information provision within organisations through the development, trialling and evaluation of guidelines that build upon existing work in the field (notably the i-access project recommendations).

The draft version of the Guidelines was trialled within the work of three organisations – IAU, EUN and the Agency – which work across the compulsory and higher education sectors. They received support and direct input from several key advisory bodies involved in technology and accessibility: the DAISY Consortium, G3ict and UNESCO.

Using sample content, digital documents (including those that could be printed), multimedia and web pages, the organisations were able to identify many of the challenges in applying the Guidelines to their work processes. These were detailed using a questionnaire, which intentionally captured important broader contextual information (please refer to Appendix B – Implementation Reports Template). Through this process, the organisations helped shape the final version of the Guidelines, and informed both this guide and a model of how to make organisations' information more accessible.

The project participants are from different phases of the education sector and each was particularly interested in making their information accessible for learning. However, the Guidelines are relevant to organisations in all fields, including the commercial and voluntary sectors, and government bodies. They provide a rationale for producing accessible information, helpful definitions,

and practical information on how this can be achieved, along with concrete examples.

Each organisation implemented the Guidelines in its own way: this suggests that the way you approach this will be specific to your organisation's context and situation. This guide attempts to bring together the key elements of success, and the recommendations detailed should inform the way in which you introduce them.

WHY YOUR ORGANISATION SHOULD CONSIDER THESE RECOMMENDATIONS

Implementing the Guidelines should be seen in the wider context of the rights of people with disabilities.

Your organisation has responsibilities and duties under international law and country legislation to ensure that people with disabilities can participate equally in society. When considering your implementation approach, it is helpful to take into account the accessibility concept as expressed in Article 9 of the UNCRPD [<http://www.un.org/disabilities/default.asp?id=269>], and how it affects your organisation as a whole. The article states:

1. To enable persons with disabilities to live independently and participate fully in all aspects of life, States Parties shall take appropriate measures to ensure to persons with disabilities access, on an equal basis with others, to the physical environment, to transportation, to information and communications, including information and communications technologies and systems, and to other facilities and services open or provided to the public, both in urban and in rural areas. These measures, which shall include the identification and elimination of obstacles and barriers to accessibility, shall apply to, inter alia:

- a) Buildings, roads, transportation and other indoor and outdoor facilities, including schools, housing, medical facilities and workplaces;*
- b) Information, communications and other services, including electronic services and emergency services.*

2. States Parties shall also take appropriate measures:

- a) To develop, promulgate and monitor the implementation of minimum standards and guidelines for the accessibility of facilities and services open or provided to the public;*
- b) To ensure that private entities that offer facilities and services which are open or provided to the public take into account all aspects of accessibility for persons with disabilities;*
- c) To provide training for stakeholders on accessibility issues facing persons with disabilities;*
- d) To provide in buildings and other facilities open to the public signage in Braille and in easy to read and understand forms;*
- e) To provide forms of live assistance and intermediaries, including guides, readers and professional sign language interpreters, to facilitate accessibility to buildings and other facilities open to the public;*
- f) To promote other appropriate forms of assistance and support to persons with disabilities to ensure their access to information;*
- g) To promote access for persons with disabilities to new information and communications technologies and systems, including the Internet;*

h) To promote the design, development, production and distribution of accessible information and communications technologies and systems at an early stage, so that these technologies and systems become accessible at minimum cost.

The importance of information and communications, specifically ICT and systems, is highlighted from the start. Other statements also have immediate implications for the production, distribution and use of accessible information, in particular 1 b), 2 a), b), c), g) and h).

One hundred and sixty State Parties have expressed their consent, by an act of ratification, accession or succession, and the UNCRPD has entered into force. Twenty-seven countries have signed and committed to consider further endorsement or ratification. Eighty-seven State Parties have, additionally, ratified the optional protocol. This shows their commitments towards implementing the UNCRPD in legislation.

More details can be viewed at: <http://indicators.ohchr.org>

Your organisation should already be addressing some or many of these issues, or be looking at some aspects of ICT or e-accessibility. However, implementing the Guidelines involves more than applying techniques that enable people with disabilities and/or special needs to overcome certain barriers. It is about leadership and resources, policy and processes and their management, standards compliance and quality assurance, education and training, social responsibility and organisational strategy.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are based on the lessons learned during the ICT4IAL project. They are intended to help organisations that want to implement the Guidelines for Accessible Information.

The seven recommendations are:

- 1) Include an accessibility statement in the organisation's long-term strategy.
- 2) Develop a strategy or plan for implementing accessible information.
- 3) Make someone responsible for implementing the information accessibility plan and provide them with the required resources.
- 4) Plan an incremental implementation – be ambitious and modest at the same time.
- 5) Embed accessibility into your information production and dissemination processes.
- 6) Provide information, education and training on accessibility for all staff.
- 7) When outsourcing information production, make sure accessibility requirements are addressed and undergo a quality check.

It is intended that you adopt the recommendations in the order that best suits your organisation. This will depend on the extent to which you have already considered the issue of information accessibility and whether you favour a top-down or bottom-up approach to addressing it.

The recommendations are closely inter-related, so addressing one of them should naturally lead to the others. If the management team wants to drive this implementation, it is advisable that you address the first three recommendations first. It is important that you include accessibility in the organisation's long-term strategy and plan for implementing accessible information; this will require a person to be responsible for its implementation.

Recommendation 1: Include an accessibility statement in the organisation's long-term strategy

Include an accessibility statement in your organisation's long-term strategy.

This can be part of your organisation's overall vision or aims statement or the detail of the operational strategy, and will depend on the nature of your organisation.

Those working in your organisation should see this public commitment to accessibility both as a driver and as permission to develop specific strategies, policy and practice to ensure you have accessible services, including digital information. Evidence from this project and from other sources has demonstrated that an accessibility statement can have a positive impact on the reach of an organisation, and the image it projects to its clients. There is some

evidence that investing in producing accessible information can result in increased income, and that making information accessible from the start is less expensive than doing it later.

If your organisation has a written statement or public commitment on accessibility, it is more likely to be addressed and to prove sustainable. This may be true even where an organisation's focus is on people with disabilities and/or special needs.

If you already have a policy that includes accessibility, but does not reference the provision of accessible information, this can be used as the starting point for implementing the Guidelines. Raise this with your management team, using the Guidelines and the recommendations in this guide to make the relevant case.

Recommendation 2: Develop a strategy or plan for implementing accessible information

Develop a clear plan of how you will implement a programme to improve the accessibility of the information your organisation develops and disseminates.

Recognising the importance of accessibility at a strategic level is very important, but should be considered as just the starting point. Translating the commitment into action requires a policy that:

- is agreed and supported by the organisation's leaders;
- has people to develop the implementation plan;
- is co-ordinated by someone authorised to ensure that it happens;
- is resourced.

Consider who should be involved in developing this plan. This is likely to depend on the nature of your organisation and should be flexible to accommodate the size, structure and cultural issues. Those involved may have a direct interest or involvement in the process, but it is particularly important to involve all relevant and affected stakeholders.

A pilot study or investigation into what is needed to improve information accessibility can act as encouragement to develop a statement that is informed by your organisation's practice. Information accessibility may not be a topic that interests everyone, but it is likely to engage many staff if it is set in the context of wider benefits for all. Professionals who work in the different areas of content production are very likely to be interested in how the techniques can benefit more people. The introduction of such a strategy will require changes to existing practice – and in some cases extra work – but those who piloted the Guidelines found the topic was popular and supported by staff in their organisations.

Ideally, your information accessibility plan should be informed by a medium- to long-term vision, which is reviewed and updated in light of the progress made. On-going developments in technology are likely to present new opportunities

and challenges for accessibility which will need to be monitored and addressed. There are increasing expectations from consumers of your information – and from society in general – for organisations to be more inclusive; therefore, your plans should be flexible and adapt to accommodate these changes.

In developing your plan, it is helpful to:

- Frame the plan using the accessibility elements relevant to your organisation, from the principles stated in Article 9 of the UNCRPD. This will place the plan within your broader strategies for accessibility, such as the physical environment and e-accessibility.
- Highlight the measures you intend to take in order to develop and sustain in-house knowledge about accessibility and how to implement it.
- Set out appropriate quality assurance measures to be included in any implementation work plans or steps.
- Consider including how you plan for accessibility to be increasingly embedded in your organisational processes and projects.
- Include a statement about compliance with international and appropriate national accessibility standards.

Even where there is no organisation strategy, statement or policy relating to accessibility, it is desirable to develop an approach to implementing information accessibility. Addressing this first can in turn lead to the development of appropriate statements and policies. Focusing on making information accessible – for example through a pilot, as in the case of the ICT4IAL project – should make it possible to raise the profile and importance of information accessibility. This can help develop the organisation's capacity to address the wider inclusion issues.

Pragmatically, although it is important to have a clear vision statement and a strategy for implementing processes and procedures to increase the accessibility of the information you produce, this may not always happen first. An important lesson from the project partners was that it is possible to raise awareness within an organisation at different levels. A bottom-up approach can complement top-down implementation. For this to be sustainable beyond any pilot process, your management team must be committed to producing accessible information. None of the organisations involved in the pilot to implement the Guidelines had a policy for information accessibility when they started. However, as a result of using the Guidelines, they now recognise that this is required and expect that a policy will be developed.

Developing and implementing an information accessibility plan requires someone in your organisation to be responsible for leading and co-ordinating the development. For the implementation to be successful, that person or team needs to have the necessary resources.

Recommendation 3: Make someone responsible for implementing the information accessibility plan and provide them with the required resources

Identify an individual or team to lead this development.

When implementing a plan to make information accessible, it helps to have an individual or a team that can act as a focal point to drive it forward. This provides a focal point for developing an implementation plan to apply the Guidelines, as proposed in your organisation's long-term strategic objectives for accessibility.

The individual or team may, for example, be involved in the final stages of information production or dissemination, have a general leadership role, or be involved in running public-facing projects or initiatives. Whether an individual or a team takes the lead will depend of the size of your organisation, or how far you have developed your overall approach to accessibility and inclusion.

The person co-ordinating the introduction of information accessibility does not necessarily need to be a senior staff member within your organisation, but must be empowered to lead on this work. This may be through recognition of the work's importance, the authority to make changes, and by ensuring adequate resources are available. Where informal arrangements exist, it is important to formalise them, so that a person who may have voluntarily promoted accessibility is recognised and authorised by the leadership team to take a proactive role.

Depending on the nature of the content produced, it may be necessary to invest in software or online tools and services to ensure it is accessible. This could incur some costs, hence the need for the person or team to be adequately resourced. However, in many cases, the software tools required are either inexpensive or use existing software's accessibility features. In these cases, the investment is more likely to be in developing the skills staff need when using these features, rather than spending money on expensive software.

Recommendation 4: Plan an incremental implementation – be ambitious and modest at the same time

Be ambitious in developing your overall plan for accessibility, as defined in your vision statement. This ambition should translate into your implementation plan, which will include all the details of what you want to achieve, with defined actions and milestones. At the same time, be realistic about the effort and complexity that may be involved.

Your organisation's starting point, in terms adopting accessibility principles, should be to establish a baseline on which to implement the information accessibility plans. The most practical starting point may be to set out small incremental changes, possibly applying the Guidelines to simple processes first, and then moving on to more complex or costly processes. Small steps

over time can lead to huge leaps in progress towards making your organisation an accessible one.

The plan should recognise the specific nature of your organisation, i.e. available resources, size, organisational complexity, and tailor the activities accordingly. Implementing changes through small steps, delivered at first through a pilot or project, is essential for sustainable implementation, but should not distract from larger objectives.

The Guidelines recommend a similar, staged approach, in terms of applying technical principles to different types of information in order to make them accessible. They recommend addressing text, images and audio as a first step. Once these are made accessible, they can be incorporated into more sophisticated media. The Guidelines also identify actions ranging from easy to professional, in terms of the knowledge levels required to use the software to create accessible information. It is helpful to consider these aspects when establishing working groups to implement the plan, along with the skill sets and processes required by those involved in producing accessible materials.

Once you have an overall implementation plan, next consider how it can be embedded into your organisation's information and dissemination processes, and the training needs that arise. It is good practice to carry out one or several defined pilot projects outside of the daily business and with a limited scope. In this way, staff will learn through applying the principles that will have a positive effect. Once proven, these principles can be incorporated into the organisation's routine business processes.

In summary, develop a flexible and incremental plan for implementing accessible information, but do not view this as an end in itself. It is important to review it regularly in order to ensure that it continues to meet the requirements of staff, of clients and of your organisation's strategy.

Recommendation 5: Embed accessibility into your information production and dissemination processes

Implement your plan and embed accessibility into your information production and dissemination processes.

Your organisation is likely to involve external third parties in producing and disseminating information. They might be authors, translators, editors, digital design companies or website developers.

Although you may not have addressed all of the recommendations suggested so far, it is likely that at some stage you will want to address the practical issue of applying the Guidelines. In order for them to become embedded in practice over time, all staff will have to make use of the Guidelines, in keeping with their role and function in the organisation.

A good starting point is to analyse your information production processes. You might set up a working group of interested stakeholders to do this. This could include, for example, those involved with the website, the information technology infrastructure, or digital services. It is sensible to include those

closely involved in producing and publishing electronic or print documents. Not everyone in the production team has to be involved, but during the Guidelines trial within the ICT4IAL project, most team members wanted to participate. It is important to include someone with a communications and dissemination role, as they will have expertise in how the content is received and used.

You probably already have a system for authoring, editing, reviewing and producing digital and print content. Analysing how you can incorporate the use of the Guidelines will help you to identify how the workflow can be adapted. Changes can be agreed to ensure accessibility is addressed at all stages of the production and dissemination process.

It is good practice to provide electronic templates and to have a style guide that includes accessibility requirements. When used by authors, editors, designers and others, this provides a set of standards for writing and designing documents, and establishes and enforces style to improve communication. Realistically, not all authors will follow the style guide or retain the required formatting in a template, so it is important to have editors and reviewers who do so. If the document is converted to a different format, a final accessibility check prior to production is essential.

Where workflows require the use of accessibility principles and are embedded into the tools everyone in the process is expected to use, this not only ensures an accessible product, but also has a wider impact. It can lead to improved awareness of the organisation's general accessibility, and to external authors adopting accessible practice in other contexts.

The Guidelines provide clear advice on the knowledge and skills required throughout the content production process. However, it is helpful to provide education and training so that staff members throughout your organisation are able to apply them. This should cover both general accessibility awareness and specialist techniques.

Recommendation 6: Provide information, education and training on accessibility for all staff

Establish an education and training programme, both to raise awareness of the importance of accessible information for all staff and in order to develop skills for those who need to apply the Guidelines.

This may seem daunting for any organisation, as technology is constantly developing and bringing new accessibility challenges and opportunities. Therefore, staff will need to learn new techniques and understand and apply new standards. All staff members, both new and established, need to stay up-to-date. Consider how your organisation can manage this.

One way to ensure staff have the required skills for applying information accessibility principles is to address this during recruitment and initial induction, and through continuous professional development plans for individuals and the organisation as a whole. The level and depth of understanding required will vary depending on the job role.

It is beneficial to have staff who are advocates for accessibility. Understanding and awareness are important elements for the adoption of changed working practice. Together with the introduction of policies for accessibility, staff training will support new ways of working.

Depending on your organisation's information production workflow, you may wish to further segment the training you offer. One example is to provide continuous professional development at three levels:

- For all staff: general awareness of accessibility and what this means in terms of production, distribution and the ways people will access the information.
- For those who create original content, such as authors: generic techniques (as per the Guidelines).
- For production and dissemination staff: knowledge and skills training on specific formats or software programs.

All staff should receive education on why accessibility and accessible information is important. Providing information, advice and educational opportunities for all staff should help to develop an environment that is receptive to accessibility and can lead to changes in the overall culture. Those who need to know how to use accessibility features in authoring and format conversion software tools should receive targeted specialist training. If, for example, your website is developed in-house, technical staff and designers should know about accessibility guidelines and standards and how to implement them.

Ensuring that your staff members are aware and equipped with the skills, tools and processes is an important success factor for implementing information accessibility. However, it is likely that third parties, rather than your own staff, will handle some information production or dissemination in your organisation. It is important that these third parties also apply the same high standards for accessibility that you do, and can demonstrate that they have done so.

Recommendation 7: When outsourcing information production, make sure accessibility requirements are addressed and undergo a quality check

When you outsource web or information content production, ensure that the developers meet accessibility requirements.

The complexity of information production often means that some or all types of media are outsourced or commissioned. As well as requiring that the Guidelines are applied across your organisation, those commissioned to produce information on your behalf should also ensure it is accessible.

Website development is usually commissioned with an external company paid to design and produce it, and you may also use third parties to create products such as videos and digital or print publications.

An i-access project recommendation is that 'accessibility should be a guiding principle for procurement of all goods and services' [<http://www.european-agency.org/agency-projects/i-access/recommendations>]. It advises only purchasing from organisations that fully account for accessibility issues. The Guidelines include details of the tools and standards for information accessibility. A recommended approach is to require that companies that tender for work demonstrate how they will comply, including details of the testing tools they will use and of the staff who have knowledge in testing.

For website development, you should specify that the development must comply with Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.0 web accessibility standards (as outlined in the Guidelines). Increasingly, countries have a legal requirement to meet this standard. Many guidance documents propose the involvement of people who use assistive technology or who have accessibility requirements. If you have staff with the necessary expertise, you may choose to manage some of this checking in-house, in order to ensure that developers have applied the appropriate techniques.

CONCLUSION

Making the information produced and disseminated by your organisation accessible provides benefits for staff and for those who use your products and services. It means that your staff and clients who have disabilities and/or special needs will be able to use that information and engage with you more effectively.

Accessible information, however, is only part of how your organisation addresses the wider expectation and requirement to treat all people fairly and equally. Broader issues include the accessibility of the built environment and how you communicate and interact with staff and customers. With an increasing focus on technology, e-accessibility is likely to be an important part of your communications strategy. Within this overall approach, information accessibility is a practical area to investigate in order to drive changes within your organisation.

The Guidelines for Accessible Information bring together in one place advice that is easy to follow, with step-by-step instructions on how to produce accessible digital documents and content. As well as useful checklists, the Guidelines include further references for those who require more detail on the techniques and tools that are available.

If your organisation adopts the recommendations in applying the Guidelines, there will be a range of benefits. These are detailed under each recommendation, and in the Abstract and Introduction sections of this guide.

Many organisations find that introducing processes for information accessibility is something that can be developed in a planned and managed way over time. A mixture of piloting new production approaches, increased awareness and education, and the management team's recognition of the importance of information accessibility can lead to real change.

Identify someone in your organisation who will take these recommendations forward. It might be you, or a group of colleagues that can address them at different levels. Ask them to look at the Guidelines and investigate how they can apply to your business processes.

Also consider the model of how your organisation could implement the Guidelines and how they might be adapted to meet your organisation's specific context and requirements.

Finally, please remember that the Guidelines and these implementation recommendations are only a starting point. Feel free to share them with others, put them on your intranet, recommend them to your web developers and to third parties you commission to develop and disseminate your information. Take ownership of them, improve on them, and share the improvements with us and with others.

If you would like to get involved and contribute to the Guidelines, as well as share your experiences on becoming a more accessible organisation, please

visit the project website [<http://ict4ial.eu/>] and register. Registration will allow you to comment on various areas of the website (in English only).

To support your implementation of the Guidelines, a model is provided outlining the interaction between policy and practice.

This is followed by a more detailed model that builds on the recommendations. It identifies considerations and processes that different stakeholders in an organisation might explore when implementing information accessibility.

A model of how your organisation could implement the Guidelines

Figure 1: How your organisation could implement the Guidelines

IMPLEMENTING ACCESSIBLE INFORMATION: A MODEL OF STAKEHOLDER CONSIDERATION

Implementation focus: Information accessibility as part of your organisation's long-term strategy

Management team	Managers	Staff	Production and dissemination specialists
<p>Consider how your business objectives and overarching strategy addresses broader accessibility issues. When reviewing organisation aims and objectives, consider how they address accessibility, including information accessibility. For example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do you take into account the principles stated in Article 9 of the UNCRPD? • Does your vision statement include 	<p>Consider how aware and responsive you are to your staff and clients' accessibility requirements. For example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are you aware of staff's accessibility needs and of the needs of those they work with or to whom they provide a service? • Does this include information provision and can you support staff in providing information that is fully accessible? 	<p>Consider whether your organisation addresses the accessibility needs of those you work with, or to whom you deliver a service. Does your organisation provide, for example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practical guidance on accessibility that you can apply, and are there routes so that you can highlight the need for such support? • Training and awareness opportunities on accessibility, including information 	<p>Consider if you need guidance and training to ensure the information outputs that you provide are accessible for all your end users. For example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do you have clear guidance or templates for forms, multimedia or other electronic content that you work on? • Are you aware of standards for accessible content design and production? • Does the organisation's style guide include

Management team	Managers	Staff	Production and dissemination specialists
<p>accessibility?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do you have an accessibility policy, and does it include accessible information? Do you have an accessibility strategy that empowers managers and staff? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can you raise this issue with the management team in order to develop a policy or improve working practice? 	<p>accessibility?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A lead person on accessibility issues, including practical concerns such as accessible information and communication? 	<p>accessibility requirements?</p>

Implementation focus: A specific strategy or plan for implementing accessible information

Management team	Managers	Staff	Production and dissemination specialists
<p>Consider how best to develop and apply a plan for making your organisation's information accessible. Your plan should:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highlight the measures you intend to take in order to develop and sustain in-house knowledge about accessibility and how to implement it. • Set out appropriate quality assurance measures to be included in any implementation work plans or steps. • Consider how accessibility will be increasingly embedded 	<p>Consider if your clients or staff members have raised the need for information to be more accessible. Have they highlighted certain difficulties or barriers to using different forms of digital content?</p> <p>If this is the case, consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raising it with the management team. • Asking if those who raised concerns are willing to be involved in activities to improve information accessibility. • Whether this indicates the need for more training on accessibility issues. 	<p>Consider if the information your organisation produces is accessible for you, your colleagues and your clients, in particular those with disabilities and/or special needs. You might consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If you are aware of barriers that should be addressed and raising them with your manager. • Asking to join a working group to develop your organisation's information accessibility plan. • Requesting awareness training on information accessibility. 	<p>Consider whether all colleagues involved in producing content have knowledge of the techniques required to ensure it is accessible.</p> <p>As a design, production or communication professional, you might consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Making your manager and colleagues aware of the Guidelines for Accessible Information. • Suggesting a pilot activity to test the Guidelines' principles. • Asking for training on the accessibility features in the software you use, or on tools for checking accessibility.

Management team	Managers	Staff	Production and dissemination specialists
<p>in your organisation's processes and projects.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Include a statement about compliance with international and appropriate national accessibility standards. 			

Implementation focus: Make someone responsible for implementing the information accessibility plan and provide them with the required resources

Management team	Managers	Staff	Production and dissemination specialists
<p>Consider designating someone to co-ordinate the implementation of your information accessibility plan. In doing this you might take into account:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Giving the lead person the authority required to implement and embed the plan. • The level of resourcing needed to fully deliver the plan. • That people involved in a range of organisational processes will need to know how to provide accessible information. • If you have an 	<p>Consider how you can contribute to the successful implementation of your organisation's information accessibility plan. For example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify if your colleagues understand accessibility, and are willing to support the person co-ordinating the implementation. • If you are directly involved in content production, offer to run a pilot or even co-ordinate the delivery of the information accessibility plan. • Ensure staff members are fully aware of the 	<p>Consider the needs of your clients, especially those with disabilities and/or special needs. If you believe your organisation could do more, why not:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offer to survey your clients' accessibility needs and provide feedback to the person co-ordinating the work on information accessibility. • Investigate the topic and ask for training if you think it would help you to understand information accessibility issues. • Offer to be involved in the group leading the 	<p>Consider working closely with the person or team co-ordinating the implementation of the information accessibility plan. Your engagement and skills are an important success factor. For example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider joining the implementation or pilot group testing the approach to implementing accessible information processes. • Identify if there are resources you need that could contribute to the process. • Can you suggest trainers or training in

Management team	Managers	Staff	Production and dissemination specialists
<p>accessibility policy, the plan co-ordinator maps stakeholders' accessibility requirements against the organisation's current information accessibility activities.</p>	<p>work on information accessibility that is taking place and encourage them to get involved.</p>	<p>work on information accessibility.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourage other colleagues to get involved. 	<p>this area that could support this work?</p>

Implementation focus: Plan an incremental implementation – be ambitious and modest at the same time

Management team	Managers	Staff	Production and dissemination specialists
<p>Consider how best to embed information accessibility into your organisation's culture, so it is sustained in the long term. Some starting points include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishing a baseline for the accessibility level of your information and electronic communications. • Deciding whether you will adopt a bottom-up pilot to look at creating accessible information, or a top-down policy-driven approach, or both. • Considering how you 	<p>Consider realistic targets for implementing information accessibility in line with your organisation's strategy.</p> <p>Encourage staff to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create presentations or documents using the organisation's templates or style guide (which have been created using the Guidelines). • Apply the built-in accessibility features in office software. • Practice what you preach – apply the Guidelines to your practice by creating accessible presentations 	<p>Consider incremental steps in learning about information accessibility that is applicable to your role within the organisation. You do not need to be an expert, but applying some basic principles will make a real difference.</p> <p>You may for example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explore the accessibility features in the software you use. • Ask for guidance on producing accessible documents or other forms of written communication. • Always follow the organisation's 	<p>Consider the specific ways you can apply accessibility to your daily practice in an increasingly systematic way. This may include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involvement in pilot activities to develop accessible content and communication work processes, in line with the Guidelines. • Learning about the advanced features of the software you use each day. • Applying technical principles to different types of information in order to make them accessible. • Encouraging a phased

Management team	Managers	Staff	Production and dissemination specialists
<p>will ensure that your organisation's accessible information provision is an iterative, developmental process.</p>	<p>and documents.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consider how to use this as a stepping-stone to encourage the adoption of other accessibility practices in your organisation. 	<p>guidelines on producing accessible information content (where these exist).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consider asking to attend a training course on accessibility. 	<p>approach that addresses text, images and audio, as a first step, and once these are made accessible, incorporating them into more sophisticated media.</p>

Implementation focus: Embed accessibility into your information production and dissemination processes

Management team	Managers	Staff	Production and dissemination specialists
<p>Consider how you can ensure that a pilot or plan for information accessibility results in practical changes to the way you produce and share information. To embed any changes it is important to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Update the business processes and related documentation to reflect the new requirements. • Monitor the new processes to ensure they are being correctly applied. • Provide the necessary training and support for those involved in 	<p>Consider strategies to support staff in applying your organisation's approach to information accessibility. This might include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness or refresher sessions on the relevant business processes. • Peer mentoring for those who undertake similar information production tasks. • Celebrating or sharing when new information types are made accessible. This might include case studies or advocates explaining the benefits this provides for end users. 	<p>Consider the difference that your organisation is making by producing information that is accessible for people with disabilities and/or special needs.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ask clients or colleagues how they benefit from the improved processes, and if further improvements can be made. • It is likely to take some time to apply accessibility principles to all the information in your organisation. You can help by updating information for which you are directly 	<p>Consider how you can make changes in practice to ensure information accessible principles are consistently and regularly applied. This might be achieved through:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working with production and communication professionals to review business processes (such as workflows). • Ensuring authors and editors have a clear understanding of their respective roles regarding information accessibility. • Developing a core set of requirements for use when procuring

Management team	Managers	Staff	Production and dissemination specialists
<p>the different aspects of content production and dissemination.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Periodically review the workflows to see if they can be improved in line with new developments in information accessibility. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrations of the use of assistive technologies with the information that has been created using the Guidelines. 	<p>responsible.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> If it is a larger product, request that the Guidelines be applied when it is revised. 	<p>accessible information products, such as websites, e-books or videos.</p>

Implementation focus: Provide information, education and training on accessibility for all staff

Management team	Managers	Staff	Production and dissemination specialists
<p>Consider incorporating information accessibility into your organisation's policy on staff development.</p> <p>Ideally, this will recognise the need for all staff to have a general overall awareness of the issues. Production and communication professionals may require more specialised training. If, for example, your organisation employs media professionals or ICT specialists you might consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing continuous professional development opportunities and 	<p>Consider how new and established staff can stay up-to-date with developments in technology, and how its application can benefit people with disabilities and/or special needs.</p> <p>You may wish to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflect on the ways you support staff in exploiting technology themselves, and understand how it can be used to support people with disabilities and/or special needs. • Explore ways to ensure that staff members have the necessary knowledge and 	<p>Consider how much you know about information accessibility.</p> <p>If you regularly produce documents that may be used by people with disabilities and/or special needs, you could ask your manager:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To provide general awareness training on the issues. • For detailed training on the benefits of and techniques to produce accessible content. • If there is a nominated expert on information accessibility issues who can provide advice 	<p>Consider how aware you are of accessibility issues relating to the technology you use.</p> <p>As a media professional (such as a journalist, broadcaster or digital production manager) or ICT specialist (such as a web designer, programmer, usability engineer or user experience designer), consider your knowledge of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disabilities and/or special needs. • Human-computer interaction strategies/alternatives for users with

Management team	Managers	Staff	Production and dissemination specialists
<p>hands-on experience.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementing incentive structures to encourage high levels of professionalism in implementing the information accessibility plan. 	<p>understanding of accessibility and the skills to apply it.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investigate how to address this during recruitment and initial induction, and through continuous professional development. 	<p>when you need it.</p>	<p>disabilities and/or special needs.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plain language as a key factor for accessibility. Accessibility policy. Assistive technology solutions.

Implementation focus: When outsourcing information production, make sure accessibility requirements are addressed and undergo a quality check

Management team	Managers	Staff	Production and dissemination specialists
<p>Consider making accessibility, including information accessibility, an integral part of your organisation's procurement policy for all goods and services. This might entail:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agreeing on the accessibility of content or electronic services during contract negotiations. • Recognising that the procurement policy is legally binding. • Including clear and attainable accessibility requirements, based on accepted standards, in all calls for tenders. 	<p>Consider how to ensure that the Guidelines are applied not only by your organisation, but also by those commissioned to produce information on your behalf.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Think about the range of external providers of information content from whom you commission or procure work. • How do you make sure that presenters at your events, writers, publishers or website developers provide accessible content? • Do you provide guidelines or templates, 	<p>Consider information accessibility when you are producing tender documents for outsourced work. Information accessibility covers a wide range of electronic and print content. It is helpful if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • You are aware of the Guidelines and the general principles of information accessibility they outline. This will help to identify different requirements when outsourcing content development or procuring digital content. • You consult a specialist 	<p>Consider the advice outlined in the Guidelines when you are commissioning third-party information. It may be helpful if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • You or your colleagues have or can develop expertise in information accessibility requirements. • Someone is able to check third parties' compliance with accessibility standards. • You can keep up with the latest developments in information accessibility, through networking or continuous professional

Management team	Managers	Staff	Production and dissemination specialists
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A process for suppliers to demonstrate that they have achieved the accessibility standards. 	require standards compliance, and have staff members who can check these have been applied?	in this area about specific requirements, if you have such a specialist in the organisation.	development. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> You involve people with disabilities and/or special needs when commissioning content and checking the content procured.

APPENDIX A – GUIDELINES FOR ACCESSIBLE INFORMATION AUDIT TOOL

The Guidelines provide clear information on the techniques you should apply to make different types of information accessible. Your organisation may find this template useful when auditing your content.

Slideshows and presentations

Applying the Guidelines to different media and specific formats	Add Y (yes), N (no) or NA (not applicable) to the next five columns and general comments in the final column	We did (try to) apply this	We found this difficult to implement	This was fairly useful	This was not useful at all	We tested this with users with print disability	Comments
	<Enter name of information resource you are testing>						
Step 1:							
Text							
	Use the simplest language which is appropriate for your document.						
	Use large fonts.						
	Use a sans serif font such as Arial, Helvetica or Verdana.						

Applying the Guidelines to different media and specific formats	Add Y (yes), N (no) or NA (not applicable) to the next five columns and general comments in the final column	We did (try to) apply this	We found this difficult to implement	This was fairly useful	This was not useful at all	We tested this with users with print disability	Comments
	Use 'Bullets and Numbering' functions for lists.						
	Avoid excessive amount of information on one slide.						
	Use text and background colour combinations that provide a very good contrast.						
	Ensure text and graphics are also understandable when viewed without colour.						
Images							
	Give your images an alternative text to describe the image.						
	Use a sufficient contrast of colours between image and						

Applying the Guidelines to different media and specific formats	Add Y (yes), N (no) or NA (not applicable) to the next five columns and general comments in the final column	We did (try to) apply this	We found this difficult to implement	This was fairly useful	This was not useful at all	We tested this with users with print disability	Comments
	background.						
	Avoid backgrounds with too many images, shapes or colours.						
	Avoid links or text being hidden behind other objects such as images.						
Audio							
	Give your audio a text equivalent.						
	Allow volume control, fast forward, rewind and pause functions.						
	Make sure captions are synchronised with your audio.						

Applying the Guidelines to different media and specific formats	Add Y (yes), N (no) or NA (not applicable) to the next five columns and general comments in the final column	We did (try to) apply this	We found this difficult to implement	This was fairly useful	This was not useful at all	We tested this with users with print disability	Comments
Video							
	Ensure captions are synchronised with your video.						
Step 2:							
	Use the slide layouts offered by your software.						
	Copy the text from the slide into the notes area.						
	Fill in the metadata information to help users find the information through internet searches.						

Online or e-learning tools

Applying the Guidelines to different media and specific formats	Add Y (yes), N (no) or NA (not applicable) to the next five columns and general comments in the final column	We did (try to) apply this	We found this difficult to implement	This was fairly useful	This was not useful at all	We tested this with users with print disability	Comments
	<Enter name of information resource you are testing>						
Step 1:							
Text							
	Use the simplest language which is appropriate for the target group.						
	Divide your information into manageable and equal blocks.						
	Use 'Bullets and Numbering' functions for lists.						
	Adopt accessible templates for consistency.						

Applying the Guidelines to different media and specific formats	Add Y (yes), N (no) or NA (not applicable) to the next five columns and general comments in the final column	We did (try to) apply this	We found this difficult to implement	This was fairly useful	This was not useful at all	We tested this with users with print disability	Comments
	Ensure your online training materials are also available in print.						
	Ensure online training can be paused, stopped and resumed.						
Images							
	Give your images alternative text to describe them.						
	Avoid use of red, green and yellow, and lighter grey colours.						
	Use a high contrast of colours between image and background.						
	Avoid backgrounds with too						

Applying the Guidelines to different media and specific formats	Add Y (yes), N (no) or NA (not applicable) to the next five columns and general comments in the final column	We did (try to) apply this	We found this difficult to implement	This was fairly useful	This was not useful at all	We tested this with users with print disability	Comments
	many images, shapes or colours.						
Audio							
	Give your audio a text equivalent.						
Video							
	Ensure captions are synchronised with your video.						
Step 2:							
	Give each page a structure by using predefined headings. Your headings should follow a logical order.						
	Offer a logical order of links, headers and all page functions						

Applying the Guidelines to different media and specific formats	Add Y (yes), N (no) or NA (not applicable) to the next five columns and general comments in the final column	We did (try to) apply this	We found this difficult to implement	This was fairly useful	This was not useful at all	We tested this with users with print disability	Comments
	for users to navigate.						
	Provide metadata when offering a range of resources. Labelling resources with relevant vocabulary or accessibility features makes it easier for the user to find relevant and accessible information.						
	Give users a sense of where they are within your website by ensuring that there is a visible or audible cue to show them where they are within the navigation.						
	Give video either a text equivalent or captions. For videos do not just give captions of the words spoken,						

Applying the Guidelines to different media and specific formats	Add Y (yes), N (no) or NA (not applicable) to the next five columns and general comments in the final column	We did (try to) apply this	We found this difficult to implement	This was fairly useful	This was not useful at all	We tested this with users with print disability	Comments
	but also provide a description of what is taking place.						
	Provide descriptions for form fields.						
	Include a search feature on each page.						
	When using interactive scenarios or cases, ensure a text equivalent is also available and can be accessed using a keyboard only.						
	Use responsive web design, which allows the content to adapt to the end users' output						

Applying the Guidelines to different media and specific formats	Add Y (yes), N (no) or NA (not applicable) to the next five columns and general comments in the final column	We did (try to) apply this	We found this difficult to implement	This was fairly useful	This was not useful at all	We tested this with users with print disability	Comments
	device.						
	Allow all page functionalities to be used through a keyboard only, including login, launch and print functions.						

PDF documents

Applying the Guidelines to different media and specific formats	Add Y (yes), N (no) or NA (not applicable) to the next five columns and general comments in the final column	We did (try to) apply this	We found this difficult to implement	This was fairly useful	This was not useful at all	We tested this with users with print disability	Comments
	<Enter name of information resource you are testing>						
Step 1:							
Text							
	Use the simplest language which is appropriate for your document.						
	Use large fonts.						
	Use a sans-serif font such as Arial, Helvetica or Verdana.						
	Use 'Bullets and Numbering' functions for lists.						
Images							

Applying the Guidelines to different media and specific formats	Add Y (yes), N (no) or NA (not applicable) to the next five columns and general comments in the final column	We did (try to) apply this	We found this difficult to implement	This was fairly useful	This was not useful at all	We tested this with users with print disability	Comments
	Give your images alternative text to describe them.						
	Use a high contrast of colours between text and background.						
	Avoid backgrounds with too many images, shapes or colours.						
	Avoid links being hidden behind other objects such as images.						
Step 2:							
	Specify the language of your document under 'properties'.						
	Avoid saving your PDF document as an image.						

Applying the Guidelines to different media and specific formats	Add Y (yes), N (no) or NA (not applicable) to the next five columns and general comments in the final column	We did (try to) apply this	We found this difficult to implement	This was fairly useful	This was not useful at all	We tested this with users with print disability	Comments
	Tag your document.						
	Use the accessibility checker offered by your software as a simple check before sharing the document.						
	Use the most up-to-date versions of software to create a PDF. Newer software versions include more up-to-date accessibility features.						
	Fill in the metadata information to help users find the information through internet searches.						
	Include all relevant elements in your document structure.						

Applying the Guidelines to different media and specific formats	Add Y (yes), N (no) or NA (not applicable) to the next five columns and general comments in the final column	We did (try to) apply this	We found this difficult to implement	This was fairly useful	This was not useful at all	We tested this with users with print disability	Comments
	Provide descriptions for form fields.						
	Ensure accessibility is not compromised when protecting PDF documents.						

Word documents

Applying the Guidelines to different media and specific formats	Add Y (yes), N (no) or NA (not applicable) to the next five columns and general comments in the final column	We did (try to) apply this	We found this difficult to implement	This was fairly useful	This was not useful at all	We tested this with users with print disability	Comments
	<Enter name of information resource you are testing>						
Step 1:							
Text							
	Use the simplest language which is appropriate for your document.						
	Use large fonts.						
	Use a sans-serif font such as Arial, Helvetica or Verdana.						
	Use 'Bullets and Numbering' functions for lists.						
Images							

Applying the Guidelines to different media and specific formats	Add Y (yes), N (no) or NA (not applicable) to the next five columns and general comments in the final column	We did (try to) apply this	We found this difficult to implement	This was fairly useful	This was not useful at all	We tested this with users with print disability	Comments
	Give your images alternative text to describe them.						
	Use a high contrast of colours between text and background.						
	Avoid backgrounds with too many images, shapes or colours.						
	Avoid links being hidden behind other objects such as images.						
Step 2:							
	Specify the language of your document.						
	Tag your document to give it structure, using the						

Applying the Guidelines to different media and specific formats	Add Y (yes), N (no) or NA (not applicable) to the next five columns and general comments in the final column	We did (try to) apply this	We found this difficult to implement	This was fairly useful	This was not useful at all	We tested this with users with print disability	Comments
	function in the software you are using.						
	Use the accessibility checker offered by your software as a simple check before sharing the document.						
	Use the most up-to-date versions of software. Newer software versions include more up-to-date accessibility features. However, make sure that your electronic document is also usable in older versions.						
	Fill in the metadata information to help users find the information through internet searches.						

Applying the Guidelines to different media and specific formats	Add Y (yes), N (no) or NA (not applicable) to the next five columns and general comments in the final column	We did (try to) apply this	We found this difficult to implement	This was fairly useful	This was not useful at all	We tested this with users with print disability	Comments
	Include all relevant elements in your document structure.						
	Avoid horizontal scrolling (scrolling from left to right or vice versa).						
	Provide descriptions for form fields.						

APPENDIX B – IMPLEMENTATION REPORTS TEMPLATE

The organisations involved in the trial implementation of the Guidelines used the following template to provide feedback. Analysis of the responses, along with other sources and expert advice, has informed the recommendations in this guide.

Your organisation may find the template a useful starting point for a pilot project. You may also consider using the audit template in Appendix A to assess the accessibility of your existing digital content.

ICT4IAL/Implementation Reports Template

A *General information about the organisation*

1. *Name of the organisation*

2. *Address/headquarters*

3. *Legal constitution of the organisation*

[Public, private; association, foundation or whatever it is.]

4. *Main objectives of the organisation*

[Short description of the organisation's main objectives.]

5. *Is the organisation an umbrella organisation?*

[Description of the organisational setting: national, international, member-based, monolingual, multilingual, etc.]

6. *How many members the organisation has [if applicable]*

7. *How the membership is composed [if applicable]*

[Short description.]

8. *How the organisation is funded*

[Short summary.]

9. *Implementing entity [part of the whole organisation]*

[Headquarters, secretariat, or whatever the implementing entity is called.]

10. *Does your organisation have a general principle/policy/strategy regarding its activities and how they are carried out?*

[Yes or no; if yes, please attach a copy of the document.]

11. *If yes, is there an accessibility statement?*

[Yes or no; if yes, please quote it here.]

12. *If yes, is there institutionalised monitoring that measures progress?*

[Yes or no; if yes, please quote the corresponding clause here.]

13. *If yes, is the monitoring systematically applied?*

[Yes, no, or statement regarding to what extent the monitoring is applied.]

14. *Is there a designated person serving as the organisation's accessibility focal point?*

[Yes or no.]

15. *Number of employees in the implementing entity*

[Figure: XY employees.]

16. *Total full-time equivalent (FTE)*

[The figure equals XY FTE.]

17. *Do the employees work in a centralised office or remotely?*

[Describe how your organisation works in this respect.]

18. *Name of the person submitting the report*

[First name, last name.]

19. *Email address of this person*

B The implementing entity as an information provider

1. Main type(s) of audience(s) for whom the published information is intended

[Short description of the audience(s) and, perhaps, their expectations.]

2. The entity's information published in several languages

[Indicate whether the entity publishes (the same) information in more than one language; if yes, how many, please list them; which is the main language; are translations performed systematically or on an ad-hoc basis?]

3. Types of information the implementing entity produces

[Indicate by Yes or No the types of information according to the following list:]

- General information:
- Guidelines:
- Standards:
- Manuals:
- Scientific reports:
- Other types: [please indicate]

4. Types of distribution

[Indicate by Yes or No the types of distribution the implementing entity uses:]

- Website:
- Electronic documents posted on the website:
- Distribution by email:
- Print:
- Others: [please indicate]

5. Criteria for the chosen distribution channels

[Indicate the criteria that determine whether you choose one or other distribution channels for specific information.]

6. Complexity in terms of structure and layout of the entity's publications [excluding the website]

[Indicate the approximate percentage (%) of your publications according to the following degrees of complexity:]

- Very simple:

[Mainly text, simple hierarchical chapter structure, no images, videos or tables, etc.; no textboxes, endnotes or footnotes, etc.]

- Medium:

[There are some images, tables, annexes, graphs or diagrams.]

- Complex:

[Same as Medium, but with a lot of images, audio, etc.]

- Advanced:

[Very complex, scientific content and even videos and interactive features.]

7. *Number of published documents a year and their size [excluding website content]*

[Indicate the approximate number of published documents the entity produces per year and their size range (numbers of pages, A4, for instance: from 2 pages to 570 pages).]

8. *Types of media [excluding the website]*

[Indicate by Yes or No whether the following types of media are used in your publications, irrespective of their prevalence.]

- Text:
- Tables:
- Graphical elements (graphs, diagrams, etc.):
- Images:
- Mathematical formulas:
- Audio:
- Video:

9. *Types of output formats the entity provides to the audience(s) [excluding the website content]*

[Indicate by Yes or No the output formats that are made available to the audience(s).]

- Word:
- OpenOffice (LibreOffice):
- PDF:
- HTML:
- Print:
- Others: [please indicate]

10. *Complexity and media used on the entity's website*

[Reply with Yes or No; please give further information if necessary.]

- Is the website public?
- Does the website have a restricted area?
- Does the website require a login process?
- If yes, describe in detail how the user login works (including, if applicable, potential advanced security measures).
- Does the website display text?
- Does the website display tables?
- Does the website display formulas?
- Does the website display audio?
- Does the website display graphical elements?
- Does the website display video?
- Does the website include forms to be filled in?
- Does the website include an online payment system?
- Does the website include links to social media (Facebook, Twitter, etc.)?

- Is the website linked with forums, blogs or similar media that include two-way communication flows?

C The implementing entity as an information producer

C1 Website content

[Does not include electronic documents in any format posted on the website.]

1. The technical implementation of the entity's website [web design and architecture] ...

[Indicate by Yes or No which is applicable or give the required reply.]

- is done in-house:
 - if yes, does the entity set WCAG 2.0 compliance as an internal requirement?
 - if not, why not?
 - if yes, does the entity test the WCAG 2.0 compliance of the product?
- is done by a third party (outsourced):
 - if yes, does the entity request compliance with the WCAG 2.0?
 - if not, why not?
 - if yes, is WCAG 2.0 compliance tested when the product is delivered?

2. Content management system [editing and posting content on the website]

[Indicate by Yes or No which is applicable; add additional information if needed.]

- The entity completely controls the content management system, including website content and electronic documents to be posted (it edits and posts content of any kind; no third party is involved):
- The content (website content or electronic documents to be posted) is posted on the website by a third party:

3. Description of the workflow when producing and posting content on the website

[Describe in detail how web content is produced and then published on the website (from authoring/editing to publishing, including all stakeholders involved).]

4. Website accessibility

[Indicate to what extent you consider your website accessible: fully accessible, partially accessible, or not accessible at all.]

- Self-assessment:

- How do you know your website is fully, partially, or not accessible at all?
- Was the website ever tested by web accessibility specialists?
- Did you ever get feedback from users regarding the website's accessibility?
- Is there a legal requirement for the entity to provide an accessible website?

C2 *Electronic document formats*

[Any electronic document format, irrespective of whether it is posted on the website or distributed through other channels.]

1. *The entity's information/publications are produced ...*

[Indicate by Yes or No which is applicable.]

- in-house:
- by a third party:
- via a mix of these two scenarios:

2. *Does the entity follow internal (mandatory) style guidelines?*

[Yes or No; if yes, please attach the guidelines to this report.]

3. *Types of production workflow(s)*

[Indicate, if applicable, which method (in-house, outsourced, mixed) you apply for which cases.]

4. *Description of the workflow(s)*

[Describe in detail **by types** of workflow (refer to C2 1.) your usual workflows:]

- idea for the information to be produced
- writing/authoring
- further editing
- proof-reading
- 'green light'
- publishing
- output format(s)

[Include which software you use, how the different output formats are produced (if applicable: when the same information is produced in Word, PDF

and HTML, for instance); include also information about who contributes to the publication during the production workflow.]

D Implementing the ICT4IAL Guidelines

D1 Starting points

1. Basic reason(s) for participating in the ICT4IAL project

[Describe the reason(s) why the organisation/entity is participating in the ICT4IAL project (for instance: internal accessibility policy requirement; demand from users/members; United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities; national legal requirement; personal interest of one or more employees, etc.).]

2. Earlier initiatives for providing accessible information

[Was/is the organisation/entity involved in any earlier initiative with respect to the provision of accessible information? If yes, which ones, policy development-oriented, concretely producing (or trying to produce) accessible information?]

3. Being aware of the accessibility ecosystem

[Yes or No: Are the people involved with the practical implementation of the ICT4IAL Guidelines aware that information accessibility is to be considered as an ecosystem that involves various accessibility dimensions? If one fails, accessibility fails; thus interoperability between the following dimensions is needed [the scope of the implementation of the Guidelines, however, is limited to the production of accessible content]:]

- accessibility of the content
- accessibility of the rendering technologies [internet, e-book reading systems]
- accessibility of the distribution channels [portals, downloads, online payment systems]
- assistive technologies [screen readers, Braille displays, other alternative input and controlling systems/devices]
- consumers that are able/enabled to use the technologies

4. Expectations

[Indicate your main expectations in relation to the implementation of the Guidelines.]

D2 *Set-up and content selection*

1. *How the Guidelines implementation project was internally set up*

[Describe in detail the approach and the processes of how you set up the Guidelines implementation project, from the first idea to practice (for instance: first communication, building an internal team [how many people], roles and functions of the team members, etc.).]

2. *Well-received initiative?*

[How the intent to implement accessibility guidelines is/was received by the stakeholders/people involved; short description; if not well received, what are the reasons put forward?]

3. *Criteria by which the entity selected the content that shall be produced in a way that it is accessible*

[Describe the criteria that guided the entity when selecting the examples of information to which the Guidelines shall be applied.]

4. *Selected content*

[List the documents to which the Guidelines are to be applied; sort the list by degree of complexity [refer to B 6.]; attach the selected documents to the present report (indicate for each whether it is an accessible document produced following the implementation of the Guidelines or an existing document that was produced earlier with no specific accessibility objectives in mind).]

- (a) Title; size (approximate number of pages [A4]); type of information [refer to B 3.]; type of complexity [refer to B 6.]; list of the media types contained in the document [refer to B 8.]; existing document or new one; short abstract of the document.
- (b) Title; size (approximate number of pages [A4]); type of information [refer to B 3.]; type of complexity [refer to B 6.]; list of the media types contained in the document [refer to B 8.]; existing document or new one; short abstract of the document.
- (c) Title; size (approximate number of pages [A4]); type of information [refer to B 3.]; type of complexity [refer to B 6.]; list of the media types contained in the document [refer to B 8.]; existing document or new one; short abstract of the document.
- (d) Title; size (approximate number of pages [A4]); type of information [refer to B 3.]; type of complexity [refer to B 6.]; list of the

media types contained in the document [refer to B 8.]; existing document or new one; short abstract of the document.

5. *Output formats to be distributed*

[Indicate for each of the selected documents the output formats you intend to distribute through one of your distribution channels.]

6. *Accessibility objectives for each of the documents and production type*

[Indicate for each of the selected documents the accessibility objectives the entity wants to achieve and the type of production workflow (refer to C2 1.).]

- Title (a)
- Title (b)
- Title (c)
- Title (d)

D3 *Implementation processes and self-assessment*

[Please repeat for each of the selected documents.]

1. *Title (a)*

[Please describe in detail the production process you applied, including the software tools used; follow the milestones in the description; if outsourced, ask the third party where necessary.]

- Preparation activities
- Authoring – software used
- Addressing the accessibility concerns (as far as applicable) [table of content, navigation, tables, formulas, serving alternate perception channels, image description, audio synchronisation, read aloud, etc.]
- Software features used to achieve the accessibility objectives
- Additional software (for instance, add-ons) used to achieve the accessibility objectives
- Further editing
- Proof-reading
- Quality assurance activity
- Validating the document's accessibility
- Printing approval
- If more than one output formats is intended, conversion from one format to the other(s)

- Validating the accessibility of the second, third, etc., output format

Title (b)

Title (c)

Title (d)

2. Self-assessment

[Please indicate whether you consider the produced documents as 'fully accessible', 'partially accessible', or 'not accessible at all'; if 'partially accessible' indicate which part you consider accessible.]

- Title (a)
- Title (b)
- Title (c)
- Title (d)

3. The produced accessible documents

[Attach the accessible documents to the present report (unless already done under D2 4.).]

E Accessibility testing of the produced documents

1. Internal testing of the produced documents and formats

[Describe (if applicable) how you did the internal accessibility testing; tools used, etc. Give the results for the different documents and formats (including print, if applicable) considering the different media [refer, for instance, to B 8.]; show the results in a matrix representation; attach it to the present report.]

2. Testing of the accessibility of the produced documents by individual end users with a print disability

[Describe (if applicable) how the accessibility testing of the produced documents and formats (including print, if applicable) was carried out by individuals with a print disability; consider the following print disabilities (if applicable) and describe the tools used for testing; give the number of testers for each print disability. Try to put the results together in a matrix and attach it to the present report.]

- People with blindness
- People with visual impairment
- People with movement disorders
- Deaf people
- Hard of hearing people
- Cognitive disorders
- Others [please indicate]

3. Testing of the accessibility of the produced documents by accessibility specialists

[Indicate (if applicable) whether a third party (agencies or similar specialised in accessibility) tested the accessibility of the produced documents; if yes, attach the reported results (including the methodologies that were applied).]

4. Overall general test result statement

[Please give a summarising statement regarding the test results in a few sentences and provide one of the following values: 'very good', 'good', 'good enough', 'not good', 'bad' or 'very bad'.]

F Experiences – lessons learned

1. General experience statement

[Give in a few sentences a general experience statement after having finalised the production of the selected documents supposed to be accessible.]

2. Difficulties and challenges encountered

[Thinking about the production workflows, what were the challenges/difficulties with respect to the aspects mentioned? The given comments are based on experience; they may be helpful when summarising your experience.]

- Authoring

[It could be, for instance, your publication comprises pieces from various authors who send you their parts in different formats, different styles, handwritten, with or (more likely) without tagging the header levels, etc. Usually, such cases complicate the production workflows and make them inefficient (not only with respect to accessibility). There may be other challenges you encountered.]

- Editing

[The editor is not necessarily the author; if not, there is an interface between authoring and editing that may cause/generate challenges; in order to minimise those challenges, corresponding processes often need to be defined/agreed on. The editor may not be familiar with the issue of accessibility at all; they may not be familiar with the built-in features or additions of the software used for creating accessible documents.]

- Proof-reading

[Normally, proof-reading processes/rounds are carried out; mainly if several people are involved, this may generate difficulties or make the process inefficient again: when specific accessibility features are overwritten and/or when an editor needs to re-integrate them.]

- Format conversion

[If you want or need to deliver more than one output format, there will be conversions from the original document format to others; these conversion processes often lead to loss of the accessibility of the original document.]

3. *Difficulties and challenges if the technical part of the production was done by a third party*

[If you handed over the technical production of a document to a third party, did you encounter specific additional challenges or difficulties?]

4. *Need for internal staff to be educated regarding accessibility*

[After having finalised the production of the accessible documents, do you see a need for education/training for those who are involved with authoring, editing and publishing information? Please indicate those needs (if applicable) for the topics mentioned, develop your thinking and give the rationales for it.]

- General education/training about what accessibility is and what it means with respect to the concrete production, distribution and consumption of information.
- Education/training on the built-in accessibility features in the software used, like Word, InDesign, etc.

5. *Need for re-thinking the workflows and internal guidelines for producing accessible information*

[After having finalised the production of the accessible documents, do you see a need to re-think the applied workflows and to establish (or revise) accordingly internal publishing guidelines that contributors to publications must follow in order to provide accessible publications?]

6. *Need for re-thinking procurement requirements if parts of the production are outsourced*

[In this case (if applicable), do you see a need for changing your procurement policy by introducing accessibility requirements? If yes, please indicate what your requirements would be.]

G *Helpfulness/usefulness of the Guidelines*

1. Usefulness of the Guidelines

[Describe in which respect and to what extent the Guidelines are useful and helped you in producing accessible information.]

2. Areas for development in the Guidelines

[Describe in which respect and to what extent you found the Guidelines less helpful and/or useful.]

3. Suggestions for more helpful and/or useful Guidelines

[Describe in details how the Guidelines can be significantly improved following your experience; please refer to the structure of the Guidelines, their language and their content.]